

MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF AL₃Ni/AL ALLOY COMPOSITE BY INFILTRATION AND REACTION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Optimization of manufacturing process of Al₃Ni intermetallic-compounds-reinforced metal matrix composite by using of the infiltration and reaction method. Objective of this study is to investigate the optimum conditions for fine intermetallic compounds dispersion inside metal matrix by different of the reaction times (60 s, 300 s and 600 s). Composites was fabricated at a molten alloy temperature of 973 K and applied pressure of 0.1 MPa; porous nickel with a specific surface area of > 5800 m²/m³ was used. The effect of counts, size, area fraction, and aspect ratio of the intermetallic-compounds inside the matrix by different of the reaction times are investigated respectively. In addition, vickers hardness and three point bending strength of intermetallic-compounds reinforced metal matrix composite was also investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to fabricate metal matrix composites (MMCs) with high performance properties by the infiltration casting technique, the squeeze casting process [1] is generally used for the infiltration because of the poor wettability between the molten metal and preform. However, if it is possible to decrease the applied pressure, the composites can be fabricated by the gravity casting [2] and low pressure casting [3,4]. These process make it possible to fabricate large, complex shaped composites. Furthermore, because these processes have high cost performance, MMCs can be used in many applications. However, the good wettability between the reinforcement causes degradation of the mechanical properties. Therefore, the improvement in the wettability is very important for fabrication of the high performance composites. The objective of this paper is to investigate the effects the reaction time on the intermetallic compounds formed is the composites by infiltration and reaction method. Therefore, we investigated the reaction between porous nickel and molten Al alloy in terms of the counts, area fraction, and aspect ratio of the intermetallic compounds for different reaction times.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A366 alloy in ASTM, which has a composition of Al-12Si-1Ni-1Cu-1Mg (mass%), was used as a matrix in this experiment. The preform was porous nickel (Toyama Sumitomo Electric Co., Ltd.). The volume ratio of porous nickel is 4~6%. Figure 1 shows SEM images of porous nickel, which has a three-dimensional network structure like sponge, large surface area, and easy machinability. Porous nickels of specific surface areas (> 5800 m²/m³) was used in the experiment to examine the reactive behavior of the intermetallic compound. Infiltration and reaction method was used to fabricate the composites. The temperature of molten Al alloy and applied pressure were 973K and 0.1MPa. This fabrication condition has been shown by previous studies to be most suitable for generation of the intermetallic compound [5]. Reaction time was controlled from 60 to 600 s. The microstructure of the composites was observed using an optical Microscope (OM) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The counts, area fraction and aspect ratio (ratio of length and width) inside matrix were measured from picture analysis using the image pro-plus software. The area analysis of each composite was conducted over an area 480mm². Flexural strength measurements were carried out using three-point bending tests. The specimen configuration and the testing condition were as

specified in ASTM C 1341. The shape of the specimen was $3^w \times 1^t \times 26^l$. The support span was 16 mm. The cross-head speed was 0.05mm/min.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Microstructures of intermetallic-compounds-reinforced metal matrix composite

Figure 2 shows the microstructure of the intermetallic-compound-reinforced composite by three difference reaction time (a; 60s, b; 300s, c; 600s). Observations of the microstructure for the composites fabricated with reaction time of 60 s (in figure 2(a)) show that almost all of the porous nickel was changed to intermetallic compound. However, almost all of the intermetallic compounds, which remain as porous nickel body without delamination from the porous nickel surface, were also observed. Therefore, unreacted nickel was observed in matrix too. Figure 2 (b) shows that most of the fine Al_3Ni intermetallic compounds were homogeneously dispersed inside matrix. When the reaction time was 300 s, more fine intermetallic compounds were distributed as compared with other materials in figure 2(a) and (c). When the reaction time was 600 s, almost all of the intermetallic compounds was distributed inside the matrix. However, many intermetallic compound, with a needle-like Al_3Ni shape, were observed as compared to a reaction time of 300 s. Figure 3 shows the results of aspect ratio (ratio of length and width) (a), counts (b) and average area (c) of intermetallic compound inside the matrix for different reaction time of 300 s and 600 s. For a reaction time of 60 s, intermetallic compounds were not dispersed inside the matrix. Therefore, the aspect ratio, counts, and average area could not be evaluated.

Figure 1: SEM images of porous nickel with a specific surface areas of $> 5800 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$

Figure 2: Microstructures of intermetallic-compound-reinforced composites; reaction time, 60 s (a), 300 s (b) and 600 s (c)

Figure 3: Aspect ratio (ratio of length and width) (a), counts and average area (b) of intermetallic compound inside the matrix for different reaction time of 300 s and 600 s.

Figure 3(a) shows the results of aspect ratio (length/width ratio) of Al₃Ni, intermetallic compounds. When the reaction time 300 s, the intermetallic compound which has the aspect ratio of 1 (granular-shaped) is 95.7% in the measured intermetallic compounds. On the other hand, when the reaction time, 600 s, the intermetallic compound which has the aspect ratio of 1 (granular-shaped) is 86.5%. When the reaction time is longer, needle-like intermetallic compounds with an aspect ratio of 3 or more mostly exist. In figure 3 (b), the counts of the intermetallic compounds analysis of each composite were determined for an area of 480 mm². Counts of intermetallic compounds Al₃Ni show an increasing trend with decreasing reaction time (300s) for the same area analysis. The average area of Al₃Ni, intermetallic compound is shown in figure 3(b). The average area of Al₃Ni shows a decreasing trend with decreasing reaction time. The results indicate that reaction time of 300 s is necessary for small sized intermetallic compounds.

3.2 Vickers hardness and Flexural strength

Figure 4 shows the results of vickers hardness of composite with a reaction time of 300 s is 198.8 Hv, higher than that observed for reaction time of 60 s (126.4Hv) and 600 s (159.1Hv); this is because

Figure 4: Vickers hardness of intermetallic-compound-reinforced composites

of the higher counts and fine intermetallic compounds inside the matrix. To comparison with aluminum alloy of matrix (80.0 Hv), vickers hardness of intermetallic-compound-reinforced composite with a reaction time of 300 s was increased 1.5 times. Three-point bending test was carried out using a composite materials with a relative density of 98%. Table 1 shows flexural strength of each composite. The flexural strength of composite with a reaction time of 300 s is 239.5 MPa, higher than that observed for reaction time of 60 s and 600 s; this is because of the higher counts and fine intermetallic compounds inside the matrix. Figure 5 shows the different fracture surface of the intermetallic compound inside the matrix. In the case with no dispersion of the intermetallic compounds (Figure 5(a)), non-reaction porous nickel was observed. it was observed non reaction nickel porous. Crack were propagated along the frame of porous nickel and ductile fracture was observed inside the matrix. In contrast, for the intermetallic-compound-reinforced composite with mostly fine microstructure, Figure 5 (b), fracture along the frame of porous nickel was not observed. Brittle fracture inside the matrix was observed by small sized intermetallic compounds. However, large sized brittle fracture inside the matrix was observed also. When the reaction time of 600 s, more large sized brittle fracture was observed inside the matrix as compared to a reaction time of 300 s. This is the cause for the decrease in strength.

Table 1: Three-point bending properties of composites.

Reaction time t [s]	Three point bending strength σ [MPa]	Fracture strain ϵ [%]
60	203.8	2.08
300	239.5	3.18
600	198.6	4.16

Figure 5: Fracture surface of intermetallic-compound-reinforced composites; reaction time, 60 s (a), 300 s (b) and 600 s (c)

4. CONCLUSIONS

Fine Al₃Ni intermetallic compounds were homogeneously dispersed inside the matrix for when the reaction time was 300 s (applied pressure of 0.4MPa, temperature of molten alloy, 973K). The counts of the intermetallic compounds, Al₃Ni, showed an increasing trend with decreasing reaction time (300 s) for the same area analysis. The average area of the Al₃Ni intermetallic compound showed a decreasing trend with decreasing reaction time. The results indicate that a long reaction time is needed for large sized intermetallic compounds. The flexural strength of the composite obtained at a reaction time of 300 s is 239.5 MPa, higher than that obtained under the other fabrication conditions.

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